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Figure 1: In what year was your organization founded?

Figure 2: How many people does your organization employ today?

How many communities or municipalities do you service?
ALL, N = 147

Figure 3: How many communities or municipalities do you service?

Is there a managing director in your utility or wastewater association?
N = 121, ALL

Figure 4: Is there a managing director in your utility or wastewater association?

How do you assess the operational freedoms of your organization vis-à-vis the municipalities?
ALL, N = 137

Figure 5: How do you assess the operational freedoms of your organization vis-à-vis the municipalities?

How do you evaluate the level of autonomy your organization has vis-à-vis the municipalities concerning governance?

ALL, N = 133

Figure 6: How do you evaluate the level of autonomy your organization has vis-à-vis the municipalities concerning governance?

What is the total area A [ha] of the association's catchment area?

ALL, N = 93

Figure 7: What is the total area A [ha] of the association's catchment area?

What is the size of the reduced area Ared [hared] connected to the WWTP in the association's catchment area?

ALL, N = 57

Figure 8: What is the size of the reduced area Ared [hared] connected to the WWTP in the association's catchment area?

**What facilities does your utility or wastewater association operate in addition to the WWTP?
N = 147, ALL**

Figure 9: What facilities does your utility or wastewater association operate in addition to the WWTP?

**How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?
ALL, N = 137**

Figure 10: How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?

**Has there been a rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the last 5 years?
N = 122, ALL**

Figure 11: Has there been a rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the last 5 years?

Are there any investments planned for the rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the next 5 years?
N = 119, ALL

Figure 12: Are there any investments planned for the rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the next 5 years?

How many pumping stations does your wastewater association operate?
ALL, N = 142

Figure 13: How many pumping stations does your wastewater association operate?

Measured variables and derived quantities in CSOs
Dies wird in allen Regenbecken gemessen. Überläufe im Kanalnetz werden nicht erfasst.
Überlaufkanten Zeit der Entlastung
aucun
quantité d'eau pluviale non traitée par dégrillage et décantation dans un bassin d'eau pluviale
Überfallmenge
aucune mesure déversser
nicht durchgängige Erfassung
Keine
Einstaudauer + Häufigkeit
50% ist ausgerüstet, bei den anderen 50% fehlt einiges
Abschlagsvolumen
Keine Messung

Table 1: Measured variables and derived quantities in CSOs

Measured variables and derived quantities in CSOs N = 127, ALL

Figure 14: Measured variables and derived quantities in CSOs

How many of your combined sewer overflows are equipped with at least one sensor device, such as Overflow detectors, Sensors to measure water depth, level or water quality, etc?
ALL, N = 126

Figure 15: How many of your combined sewer overflows are equipped with at least one sensor device, such as Overflow detectors, Sensors to measure water depth, level or water quality, etc?

How many permanent rain gauges does your wastewater association operate?
ALL, N = 138

Figure 16: How many permanent rain gauges does your wastewater association operate?

How is the water level/spill data transmitted by the measuring devices?
Aucune donnée
Es werden noch immer keine Entlastungs- oder Niveaudaten in SBW gemessen. Erste Abklärungen beginnen 2025.
aucun
relevé manuel
pas de mesure
Funk
pas de sonde niveau déversoir
keine
Vorort
Werden nicht übertragen
Tetra
Radio
GPRS/IP
Keine/Übertragung

Table 2: How is the water level/spill data transmitted by the measuring devices?

How is the water level/spill data transmitted by the measuring devices?

N = 147, ALL

Figure 17: How is the water level/spill data transmitted by the measuring devices?

In our opinion, the cause of the poor data quality lies in...
Fehlendes Messkonzept, da bisher keine Verpflichtung zum Messen/Überwachen und gleichzeitig fehlender "Behördendruck" (es wird nichts gefordert und daher auch nichts regelmässig kontrolliert).
Pas d'envie
pas de mesure
Zu wenig Messgeräte
Kapazität um Projekte anzugehen
Keine Messung
Betreuung
Eigentum der Gemeinden
Manglende fokus på D&V af sensorerne og manglende forståelse for hvad data skal bruges til
Bauform

Table 3: In our opinion, the cause of the poor data quality lies in...

**From how many installations are the data transmitted directly to the DCS of the WWTP?
ALL, N = 135**

Figure 18: From how many installations are the data transmitted directly to the DCS of the WWTP?

**How often are the water level/spill data evaluated for performance assessment?
ALL, N = 135**

Figure 19: How often are the water level/spill data evaluated for performance assessment?

**The quality of our water level monitoring data in our organization is good?
N = 116, ALL**

Figure 20: The quality of our water level monitoring data in our organization is good?

We have the following problems:
Fehlende Fachleute
Zusammenarbeit Abwasserverband und Gemeinden existiert kaum

Table 4: We have the following problems:

In our opinion, the cause of the poor data quality lies in...

N = 23, ALL

Figure 21: In our opinion, the cause of the poor data quality lies in...

We have the following problems:

N = 23, ALL

Figure 22: We have the following problems:

Our organization shares the water level data with third parties ...
AFU
Die Daten werden als 15 Minuten Mittelwert gespeichert und für eine mögliche Umstellung auf eine dynamische Bewirtschaftung des Kanalnetzes archiviert
Canton de Vaud DGE
avec le SEN
Partenaires pour études
nog niet
DDT, agence
BE dans le cadre d'études

Table 5: Our organization shares the water level data with third parties ...

What are the reasons that would motivate you most to use measurement technology at urban drainage systems?
Nur Wasserstandmessung

Table 6: What are the reasons that would motivate you most to use measurement technology at urban drainage systems?

Our organization shares the water level data with third parties ...

N = 147, ALL

Figure 23: Our organization shares the water level data with third parties ...

What are the reasons that would motivate you most to use measurement technology at urban drainage systems?

N = 20, ALL

Figure 24: What are the reasons that would motivate you most to use measurement technology at urban drainage systems?

Where do you see the biggest obstacles to the use of measurement technology for your wastewater association?
fehlende Messtechnik
Übermittlung von Daten
fehlende Personalkapazität
Im Besitz der Gemeinden und wird über Bauämter und GEP Ingenieure gemacht ohne den Abwasserverband

Table 7: Where do you see the biggest obstacles to the use of measurement technology for your wastewater association?

Why did your wastewater association decide to use measurement technology on the plants?
Mål fra kommune - Spildevandsplan
SüwVO Abw

Table 8: Why did your wastewater association decide to use measurement technology on the plants?

Where do you see the biggest obstacles to the use of measurement technology for your wastewater association?
N = 29, ALL

Figure 25: Where do you see the biggest obstacles to the use of measurement technology for your wastewater association?

Why did your wastewater association decide to use measurement technology on the plants?
N = 60, ALL

Figure 26: Why did your wastewater association decide to use measurement technology on the plants?

Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc)
ALL, N = 105

Figure 27: Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc); Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc) [Comment]

Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc); Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc) [Comment]
Wir versuchen die Messdaten sstetig zu plausibilisieren
Sensoren werden überwacht, Plausibilisieren im Rahmen der Kontrollgänge
Pas de DO dans la commune
Keine Unsicherheitsbetrachtung, weil keine Messdaten erhoben werden von den SBW im Einzugsgebiet.
nous n'avons pas de bassin tampon
Alle Messungen werden bei der IBS Referenziert. Die Daten sind sehr genau und korrespondieren gegeneinander
Die Angaben sind von einer sehr kleinen ARA, somit eher irrelevant!
Plausibilisierung des gelieferten Abwassers pro Gemeinde an die Kläranlage
Ritune mit Datenvisualisierung und Plausibilisierung
Ja, vi kigger på om der er sammenhæng med overløb og andre påvirkninger. F.eks. høj vandstand i vandløb der giver tilbagestuvning i systemet. Vi laver ikke deciderede usikkerhedsberegninger.
Der laves en usikkerhedsvurdering, men ikke en usikkerhedsberegning.
Je pense que cela est nécessaire mais très difficilement réalisable au vu de la complexité déjà éprouvée pour faire des mesure de volumes déversés.
Les données sont validées ou invalidées sans calcul d'incertitude.
Trending der Daten

Table 9: Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc); Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc) [Comment]

Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?
N = 106, ALL

Figure 28: Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?

Do you think it makes sense for the wastewater operator to operate both the WWTP and all urban drainage systems in the long term?
Es ist sinnvoll die Kommunikation zwischen den Betreibern zu fördern
Mitwirken in der Planung von Entwässerungsanlagen
verrohrte Gewässer nicht sinnvoll
il est judicieux de prendre en charge au moins les ouvrages principaux sur l'ensemble du bassin versant

Table 10: Do you think it makes sense for the wastewater operator to operate both the WWTP and all urban drainage systems in the long term?

Have you completed an integrated drainage plan at the level of your wastewater association?
N = 98, ALL

Figure 29: Have you completed an integrated drainage plan at the level of your wastewater association?

In what year was this IDP approved?
ALL, N = 73

Figure 30: In what year was this IDP approved?

Is this IDP currently being revised as part of the drainage planning?
N = 76, ALL

Figure 31: Is this IDP currently being revised as part of the drainage planning?

How far do you agree with this statement: Our organization cooperates well with regulatory authorities for urban drainage
ALL, N = 129

Figure 32: How far do you agree with this statement: Our organization cooperates well with regulatory authorities for urban drainage

Have employees of your wastewater association participated in one of the following professional events within the past year? Trade fair (IFAT) National association meeting (e.g. working group meeting) National urban drainage conference (CIWEM, Aqua Urbanica, GRAIE, AEOPAS, ...) Event of the regulatory office in the field of urban drainage Customer event of engineering consultancy Customer event of a company related to measurement technology or automation
N = 140, ALL

Figure 33: Have employees of your wastewater association participated in one of the following professional events within the past year? Trade fair (IFAT) National association meeting (e.g. working group meeting) National urban drainage conference (CIWEM, Aqua Urbanica, GRAIE, AEOPAS, ...) Event of the regulatory office in the field of urban drainage Customer event of engineering consultancy Customer event of a company related to measurement technology or automation

Has your wastewater association already commissioned a third party (e.g. electrical or engineering consultant) to carry out the maintenance of the measurement technology (e.g. regular cleaning and calibration of measuring instruments) or to evaluate measurement data?
ALL, N = 126

Figure 34: Has your wastewater association already commissioned a third party (e.g. electrical or engineering consultant) to carry out the maintenance of the measurement technology (e.g. regular cleaning and calibration of measuring instruments) or to evaluate measurement data?

Figure 35: Do you think it makes sense for the wastewater operator to operate both the WWTP and all urban drainage systems in the long term?

A possible vision of the future: "Stormwater systems and sewer networks are equipped with a large number of measuring devices. The measurement signals are transmitted live to a control system via a nationwide wireless network, automatically checked, evaluated and archived. This permanent monitoring of the systems is made possible by the advancing technological development in the areas of communication, control and automation technology." What do you personally think of the vision described?; Vision 1: "Real-Time Monitoring and Evaluation of Stormwater and Sewer Systems"
Da wir die Messtechnik selber installieren und die dafür nötigen Übertragungsmedien auch, ist mir eine Draht, Glas gebundene Einbindung zuverlässiger. Auch kann so die Verifizierung einfacher erfolgen.
Je nach Charakter des Einzugsgebiet und der Belastung der ARA kann der Einsatz flächendeckender Messungen und deren direkten Einfluss auf die Systemsteuerung Sinn machen. Sofern der Betrieb der Anlage weitgehend statisch funktioniert, ist diese Lösung auch interessant.
Kosten müssen überschaubar sein.
Wird in unserem Verband im Jahr 2027 Realität sein, wir arbeiten bereits aktiv daran.
Wo auch immer möglich und sinnvoll einsetzbar.
Kommunikations- und Stromversorgungsprobleme sind nicht überall einfach zu lösen
wenn auf die ermittelnden Daten nur die jeweilige Kläranlage bzw. der Verband Zugriff inklusive der zuständigen Behörden.
Reduktion auf die absolut notwendigsten Messgeräte.
Wenn sie pragmatisch und sinnvoll angewendet wird
På organisationsniveau til monitorering, planlægning, styring etc.
Forståelsen af data afhænger af forståelsen af målepunktet. Det vil kræve en del ift. registrering af metadata, at gøre data brugbare. En niveaumåling i et overløbsbygværk der ikke bliver omregnet til koter, er svære at bruge for andre.
Driftsøkonomi skal kunne dækkes ind ved besparelse. Ofte er stor overvågning endt i stort rod.
Betreiben wir in Teilen schon, wird weiter ausgebaut.
Un contrôle régulier des appareils de mesure pour éviter des pertes de données ou autres dysfonctionnement
Les mesures sont gérées par bassin versant de STEP ou bassin hydrologique. La gestion des flux doit pouvoir être dynamique et l'association dispose des compétences pour l'analyse et l'exploitation des données.

Table 11: A possible vision of the future: "Stormwater systems and sewer networks are equipped with a large number of measuring devices. The measurement signals are transmitted live to a control system via a nationwide wireless network, automatically checked, evaluated and archived. This permanent monitoring of the systems is made possible by the advancing technological development in the areas of communication, control and automation technology." What do you personally think of the vision described?; Vision 1: "Real-Time Monitoring and Evaluation of Stormwater and Sewer Systems"

Figure 36: A possible vision of the future: "Stormwater systems and sewer networks are equipped with a large number of measuring devices. The measurement signals are transmitted live to a control system via a nationwide wireless network, automatically checked, evaluated and archived. This permanent monitoring of the systems is made possible by the advancing technological development in the areas of communication, control and automation technology." What do you personally think of the vision described?; Vision 1: "Real-Time Monitoring and Evaluation of Stormwater and Sewer Systems"

Figure 37: Vision 2: "Publicly Accessible CSO Data for Enhanced Collaboration and Sustainability"; Another possible vision of the future: "In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices." What do you personally think of the vision described?

Figure 38: Is the legal basis available for performance monitoring of CSOs (law?)

Vision 2: "Publicly Accessible CSO Data for Enhanced Collaboration and Sustainability"; Another possible vision of the future: "In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices." What do you personally think of the vision described?
Es gibt kein Personal die das unterhalten und aufbauen können, wo auch die nötigen Zusammenhänge verstehen
Fehlmessungen können Bevölkerung unnötig (mangelndes Verständnis) beunruhigen. Mit Aufsichtsbehörde/Fachgremien kein Problem.
Aufgrund unserer Erfahrung ist es jeweils notwendig, die Daten sehr gut zu prüfen und teilweise sind auch entsprechende Zusatzinfos über die Qualität zu ergänzen.
Es sollten nicht die Rohdaten, sondern plausibilisierte und ev. aufbereitete Daten öffentlich zugänglich sein. Es kann sonst zu Verwirrungen führen
Mit Subventionen
Qui va s'y intéressé à pars les professionnels
Wenn kein Zugriff auf interne Systeme erfolgen kann.
Solange der Kanton nicht bereit ist die Strassenentwässerungen zu trennen, sehe ich hier leider nur geringen Nutzen.
Der Aufwand dafür erscheint mir sehr hoch
L'exploitation des données peut mettre en danger le système d'assainissement. De plus, les données brutes doivent régulièrement être validées manuellement pour invalider des aberrations.
Para los que no sean OC se facilite una información resumida un nunca en tiempo real. una cadencia de una vez al año me parece lógica.
goede afspraken met datagebruikers over het verder gebruik van deze data (data governance)
Vi indberetter alle udløb til PULS, så alt er allerede offentligt tilgængeligt.
Der skal være mulighed for at validere data først, dvs. det bliver ikke i realtid. Ellers kan jeg være bekymret for at data kan blive misbrugt.
Cela peut faire prendre conscience du besoin de séparer les eaux et de l'impact sur les milieux
Ist kritische Infrastruktur.
que cette mesure soit accompagnée avec une sensibilisation sur le fonctionnement d'un système d'assainissement
Die Daten sind so aufzubereiten, dass keine falschen Interpretationen gemacht werden. Die Aufbereitung generiert aber einen zusätzlichen Aufwand.
Die Daten sollen vor der Veröffentlichung geprüft und plausibilisiert werden
Dies ist nicht notwendig da es zu Fehlinterpretationen führen kann ohne das notwendige Anlagenspezifische wissen.
Les données ayant une incidence sur la santé publique peuvent être rendues publiques. La transparence complète peut inciter à mettre trop de pression pour prendre des mesures rapides et non réfléchies, non efficaces à un niveau global.
Es soll vom Inhaber frei wählbar sein, welche Parameter öffentlich gemacht werden. Gefahr, "anden Pranger" gestellt zu werden. Schlechte Performance des Kanalnetzes ist nicht zwingend gleichbedeutend mit einem schlechten Job der Inhabenden / Betreibenden

Table 12: Vision 2: "Publicly Accessible CSO Data for Enhanced Collaboration and Sustainability"; Another possible vision of the future: "In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices." What do you personally think of the vision described?

Is a legally binding implementing ordinance/ regulation available?
N = 83, ALL

Figure 39: Is a legally binding implementing ordinance/ regulation available?

Are there technical standards and guidelines available?
N = 96, ALL

Figure 40: Are there technical standards and guidelines available?

Are the existing regulations applied by the operator?
N = 97, ALL

Figure 41: Are the existing regulations applied by the operator?

Are the existing regulations are enforced by all actors?

N = 84, ALL

Figure 42: Are the existing regulations are enforced by all actors?

How are existing CSO structures regulated?
Dynamischer Betrieb über PLS
Kanalbewirtschaftungssystem
Aucun DO sur la commune
Kanalnetzbewirtschaftung
-
déversement pas de mesure
Auffangen erster Schmutzstoss. Wenn Zulauf ARA es zulässt kann Entleerung RÜB begonnen werden.
Eksisterend overløb har vi ikke deciderede krav til frekvens og voloumener. I nyhe tilladelser bliver der stillet krav til gns. volumener og gns. antal overløb pr. år.
Gennem en udledningstilladelse, der kan gå både på mængder og antal. Dog bliver definitionen af et overløb sjældent specificeret, så det er reelt svært at forholde sig til antal.
Ab 2025 Zentrale Bewirtschaftung vom PLS

Table 13: How are existing CSO structures regulated?

How are existing CSO structures regulated?

N = 147, ALL

Figure 43: How are existing CSO structures regulated?

Policy	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Normalized score
Standards and technical guidelines for equipping the systems with measurement technology (e.g. water level measuring device in the CSO)	45	25	15	1.0
Environmental protection targets (e.g. measured values of water level in the CSO, flow rate in the sewer)	33	24	13	0.8
Shifting competence from the municipality to the association	16	14	10	0.43
Increased supervisory role of the cantons	9	9	8	0.26
One-off subsidy for metrology equipment	6	8	13	0.24
Performance indicators	5	9	14	0.24
Participation in the running costs of the maintenance of the measuring instruments and the evaluation of the measurement data	2	9	12	0.18
Better products and services from metrology companies	6	7	3	0.18
Customized services of engineering and design offices	3	7	12	0.18
Education and training opportunities for measurement technology and measurement data management	1	10	10	0.16
Joint events and information campaigns	2	6	7	0.12
Own suggestion	2	0	3	0.04

Table 14: What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs?

Write your proposal for the question: What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs?
Die Kommunen müssen Infrastruktur gemeindam nutzen und freigeben für Datenübermittlung
Engagement der Verantwortlichen Personen ist entscheidend
Mitwirken und Einbezug bei Überbauungsplanungen, Trennsysteme und Sanierungsmassnahmen in den Gemeinden.
Das Bewusstsein für die Aufgaben und Funktion des Kanalnetzes muss gefördert werden. Aktuell wird für jede ARA ein Jahresbericht erstellt, welcher eine Leistungsbeurteilung enthält. Eine Beurteilung über die Leistung des Kanalnetzes fehlt in der Regel.
Verbindliche rechtliche Grundlagen von Seite Kanton/Staat

Table 15: Write your proposal for the question: What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs?

Apply to be part of an Co-UDLabs early adopter group of innovative utilities to share experiences regarding CSO and data management.
N = 146, ALL

Figure 44: Apply to be part of an Co-UDLabs early adopter group of innovative utilities to share experiences regarding CSO and data management.

Do you have any further comments or ideas on the topic of "Water protection during wet weather - organization of urban drainage" or on our questionnaire?
Das ganze Thema ist sehr sehr individuell auf das Einzugsgebiet der ARA zu betrachten
Das AIB als Amt beschäftigt 68 MA und ist für 78 Gemeinden im Kanton BL zuständig (4 Einzugsgebiete). Aus Synergiegründen ist es nicht möglich die Anz MA nur für das EZG E1 anzugeben. Alle weitere Angaben sind auf das EZG Ergolz 1 abgestimmt und aus dem GEP EZG Ergolz 1 entnommen (CSO, Fläche).
- Qualität des Fragebogens nicht über alle Zweifel erhaben (teilweise wirre Fragestellungen, gemixt mit Englisch)
La STEP reçoit la totalité des eaux du territoire communal, tant les eaux usées que les eaux de pluie, le réseau d'assainissement étant en système "unitaire". L'exutoire étant unique, il n'est pas possible de concevoir un réseau selon le système séparatif dans un rapport coût/ efficacité acceptable. Nous avons construit en 2022 un nouvel ouvrage pour dégriller quatre fois plus les eaux qui ne transitent pas par la STEP, soit 8 m3/s, réduisant considérablement le rejet de déchets à l'exutoire (40 x moins). Ainsi, en multipliant par quatre la capacité de dégrillage, cela diminue de 90% le volume d'eau déversé dans la rivière sans dégrillage, ramenant cette quantité à moins de 1% du débit des eaux non traitées, soit, en moyenne, un seul événement de pluie par année. La quantité de déchets grossiers rejetés dans l'environnement est ainsi réduite de 95%.
Ihre Umfrage geht davon aus, dass im Mischsystem entwässert wird. In unserem Einzugsgebiet trifft dies nur auf eine untergeordnete Anzahl der Siedlungsflächen zu.
Unsere ARA für rund 500 Einwohner funktioniert nach dem Trennsystem, das bedeutet ein relativ konstanter Schmutzwasseranfall und nur sehr geringer Anteil an Regenwasser.
Die Leute fordern das keine Überfälle mehr vorkommen. Die Kantone und teilweise auch die Kommunen machen aus unserer Sicht jedoch zu wenig um Unverschmutztes Abwasser konsequent aus der Schmutzwasserkanalisation zu entfernen. Oftmals werden noch heute Strassen Mischsystem erschlossen statt auf SABAs zu setzen. Die Verantwortung für die Überfälle liegt danach bei den ARAs
Mesurer le débit déverser avec analyse pour voir l'impacte de pollution .
Bei uns werden alle RB überwacht
Teilweise unklare Fragen.
Da RÜB bei uns von der Grösse und der Pumpleistung die Begrenzung festlegen (Mechanisch - wenn voll, restlicher Zulauf läuft über), macht es keinen Sinn da zu messen! Arbeit der Arbeit willen, ohne dass etwas geändert werden kann bringt nichts!
Bei langen Regenwetterperioden mit schlechtem Trennsystem könnte die Wasserqualität bestimmt werden im RüB. Damit könnte die ARA Energie sparen. Konkret: Ara abstellen, da nur noch Regenwasser gereinigt wird.
Dans le cadre des ARD il serait judicieux de convenir pour les A1 télésurveillé de mettre en place des alarmes "déversement temps sec", de faire remonter les potentiels défaut voir anomalies de fonctionnement (rejets conséquent des industriels sur de faible pas de temps)
On attend de voir ce que va donner la DERU 2.
Obligation par la loi d'indexer le prix de l'eau sur le cout de la vie....pour permettre de maintenir le niveau de service sur le long terme
Remarque générale sur questionnaire : la distinction entre STEP et réseau aurait pu être pertinente, car les caractéristiques et données sont parfois différentes entre les deux.
Unsere Anlage wird bald rückgebaut und das Abwasser in eine andere, neue Anlage gepumpt. Die Kanäle und Entlastungen sind 40 jährig und sollten am Ende ihrer Lebensdauer von 80 Jahren frühzeitig mit der neuen ARA zeitgemäss umgerüstet bzw. geplant und überwacht werden (Bewirtschaftung über Leitsystem der neuen ARA).
Langfristiger Systemwechsel zu vermehrt dezentraler Abwasserentsorgung / Bewirtschaftung, weg von Schwemmkanalisation hin zu Bewirtschaftung der Abwasserbestandteile (Wasser und Feststoffe) als wertvolle Ressourcen, in dem die natürlichen Stoffkreisläufe möglichst wiederhergestellt werden.

Table 16: Do you have any further comments or ideas on the topic of "Water protection during wet weather - organization of urban drainage" or on our questionnaire?